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The Coach-Athlete Relationship and School Experience as the Determinant of Sports-Specific Life Satisfaction

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Abstract

The present study is aimed at determining coach athlete relationships, perceived school experiences and sports life satisfaction levels of athlete high school students and to examine the levels based on certain variables. The sample of the research consisted of a total of 306 students, 117 (38.2%) male and 189 (61.8%) female, who continued their education at different high schools in Trabzon in the 2019-2020. "Personal Information Form" designed by the researcher, "The Coach-Athlete Relationship Questionnaire (CART-Q)," "The Sport-Specific Satisfaction with Life Scale (SSWLS)" and "Perceived School Experiences Scale (PSES)" were used as data collection tools in the research. In the statistical method of the study, descriptive statistics, t-test, pearson correlation tests and regression tests were used. In the research findings, while there was a significant difference in the sub-dimensions of the coach-athlete relationship and sportive life satisfaction according to gender, no significant difference was found in the perceived school experiences. A significant difference was found in all scales and sub-dimensions according to the status of playing in the school team. As a result, a high level of positive correlation was found between the coach-athlete relationship and sportive life satisfaction, and between perceived school experiences and sportive life satisfaction. In addition, another important result is that the coach-athlete relationship (51%) and school experiences (32%) have important roles in predicting the satisfaction with sportive life.

Keywords: Student Athlete, Coach, Experience, Life Satisfaction

1. Introduction

Countries develop various policies to raise young generations and maintain these policies by applying them in the educational environment. If we include sports policies in these policies, the concept of athlete student, which will make this expansion and make a great contribution, has an important place (Çetinkaya, 2019). International organizations state that doing sports and active participation in sports have positive effects and they implement many programs (World Health Organization [WHO], 2010; Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2013).

School is seen as the second most influential institution on the individuals (Çaplı, 1993). Education and sports are two indispensable touchstones for individuals and society. Therefore, the important responsibilities of families and schools, especially teachers and trainers, should not be ignored in the joint conduct of education and sports, understanding the benefits of sports, and disseminating sports to all layers (Hergüner, 1992). There are studies in the literature that participation in sports activities increases academic achievement and contributes positively to the development of perception towards school (Göktaş & Şentürk, 2019; Öcal & Koçak, 2010; Özdoğru, 2018; Linder, 1999; Saygılı, Atay, Eraslan & Hekim, 2015; Singh, Uijtdewilligen, Twisk, Van Mechelen, & Chinapaw, 2012; Whitley, 1999). In addition to the cognitive and socio-emotional benefits of students' orientation to sports activities outside of school, it also contributes to the desired development and learning results with school curriculum programs (Özdoğru, 2018).

From another point of view, athlete students are in contact with their teacher at school and with their trainer during training. In order to be successful in education, the relationship between the teacher and the coach should be positive for effective performance in sports. The relationship between the coach and the athlete should not be ignored in success in sports (Martens, Christina & Harvey, 1981). It is thought that the perception of the behaviors of the coach observed by the athlete significantly affects the performance of the athlete, and examining the studies from this framework is of great importance for successful or effective coaching (Altıntaş, Kazak-Çetinkalp & Aşçı, 2012). The coach-athlete relationship plays an important role in athlete performance (Güven & Öncü, 2012) and athletic success (Sunay & Saracaloğlu, 2003). Researchers have stated that the quality of the coach-athlete relationship, the character and performance of the athlete (Jowett & Cockerill, 2003), the concept of self (Jowett, 2008), internal motivation (Felton & Jowett, 2013) contributes to development sports satisfaction (Jowett & Nezlek, 2011), athlete and coach life satisfaction (Jowett & Poczwardowski, 2007), team cohesion (Jowett & Chaundy, 2004) and collective effectiveness (Hampson & Jowett, 2014).

Another subject of the research is the school experiences of the athletes. Perceived school experience is also of great importance for individuals with dual careers. The knowledge and experiences of students about school throughout their school life constitute their school experiences (Akin et al, 2013). The term of perceived school experience was conceptualized by Butcher, Amorose, Iachini & Ball (2012) by gathering the concepts of school commitment, academic motivation and academic pressure in the literature under one umbrella term, and it has found an area of application in Turkish literature with the studies of Akin and Sarıçam (2014). Studies on perceived school experiences (Akin, 2015; Baytemir, 2019; Baytemir, Kösterelioğlu, & Kösterelioğlu, 2015; Güler, 2019; Özkara & Kalkavan, 2018) are found in the literature. Jowett and Nezlek (2011) reported that the coach-athlete relationship is effective in the life satisfaction of the athletes, and contentment between the two increases the duration and quality of the relationship.

The fact that the relationship of the coach-athlete relationship has an important place in increasing the performance of the athlete has become one of the popular topics today, especially in our country, the insufficient number of studies in this field and the will to reach important results with the obtained findings have laid the groundwork for the studies. In short, athlete students lead a life with their school experiences, sports activities, relationships with their teachers or trainers and other experiences. The more positive these experiences are, the higher the performance in sports activities and the more success in the field of education. If these experiences of the athletes are negative or they cannot overcome the difficulties they experience, their educational success and sportive performance may also decrease. When considered from a psychological point of view, the satisfaction received from sports life will also decrease and will be affected in many ways. In this context, the aim of the research is to compare the perceived school experiences, coach-athlete relationship and sportive life satisfaction according to the determined variables, to reveal their relations with each other and to reveal whether the coach-athlete relationship and perceived school experiences have an effect on sportive life satisfaction.

2. Method

2.1. Research Model

The research was carried out with the screening method within the framework of the quantitative approach. The scanning method, which describes the pre-existing and present situation as it is (Kuzu, 2013), is to be able to convey the situation, person or object under investigation as it exists within the existing conditions and to observe the conditions without changing them (Karasar, 2012).

2.2. Research Group

The study group of the research consists of a total of 306 athlete students, 189 female and 117 male, studying at schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education in the 2019-2020 academic year. These students are between the ages of 14 and 18 (Mean age = 16.16 ± 1.28). In addition, 192 of the students are athletes in school teams, while 114 of them do not play in any school team.

2.3. Sampling Procedures

In order to determine the group (sample) to represent the research, first the research proposal was presented to the Ministry of National Education, General Directorate of Innovation and Educational Technologies, and after the necessary permissions were obtained, a survey was conducted at schools on a voluntary basis by using the "Easy to Find Sampling" method. Sampling that can be found easily, if it does not cover a region in question, is the sampling made on volunteers who are in the immediate vicinity and can be easily reached (Erkuş, 2009). In addition, this method brings speed and practicality to the researcher (Şimşek & Yıldırım, 2005).

2.4. Data collection

The "Personal Information Form" designed by the researcher, "The Sport-Specific Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS)," Perceived School Experiences Scale (PSES) and The Coach-Athlete Relationship Questionnaire (CART-Q) were applied to collect data in the study.

2.4.1. The Sport-Specific Satisfaction with Life Scale (SSWLS)

The Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS), developed by Diener, Emmons, Larsen, and Griffin (1985), consists of 5 items and a 7-point scale adapted to sports by Mangan (2018). Diener et al. (1985) stated that in the factor analysis of the scale, it explained 66% of the total variance with a single factor and the internal consistency of the scale was .87. Mangan (2018) found the Cronbach α coefficient for internal consistency to be .89. The adaptation study of SSWLS was adapted to Turkish by Somoğlu (2021). In the results of the analysis performed during the adaptation process, the linguistic equivalence of the scale was found to be significantly positive between the two forms (English and Turkish) of SSWLS ($r = .97, p < .01$). In the content validity study, he stated that the Content Validity Index score ($0.96 > 0.62$) obtained for the 5 statements of the SSWLS scale was at a good level when the Content Validity Criterion was taken into account. As a result of the EFA findings, it was determined that the total explained variance was 81,730%. The eigenvalues of the scale items were determined as a result of EFA, which combined under a single factor greater than 1. It was stated that the ratio of the CFA chi-square value to the degrees of freedom ($8,898 / 5 = 1,780$) had a good fit level below 5. When the fit indices RMSEA= .057, SRMR= .039, GFI= .986, NFI= .992, RFI= .984, CFI= .996 and IFI= .996 were examined, it was revealed that the model fitted well and the model was fit. As a result of similar scale validity analysis, a moderate level of .50 between the Sports-Specific with Contentment with Life Scale and a .68 level close to high correlation between the Sports-Specific with Life Satisfaction Scale and the Athlete Identity Scale were found. Cronbach alpha internal consistency reliability coefficient of Sports-Specific with Life Satisfaction Scale. It was found to be 0.87. As a result of the retest reliability analysis, it was determined that there was a highly significant positive correlation between the two applications ($r = .89, p < 0.01$). As a result of the item-total correlation analysis to determine the differences between the 27% upper-lower group items of the SSWLS, it was stated that

the item-total correlations of the Sports-Specific with Life Satisfaction Scale scored between .89 and .92, and the t-values were significant ($p < .001$).

2.4.2. Perceived School Experiences Scale (PSES)

The Perceived School Experiences Scale includes the three basic concepts of school engagement (SC), academic motivation (AM) and academic pressure (AP) (Butcher et al., 2012) dimensions to determine students' perceptions of school life. Butcher et al. (2012) and adapted into Turkish by Akin and Sariçam (2014). The item pool of the scale was composed of 32 items, and as a result of the EFA analysis, a structure consisting of 16 items and 3 sub-dimensions was obtained. As a result of the CFA analysis, the scale items took their final form consisting of 14 items and sub-dimensions. The scale is in 5-point Likert format and the total score that can be obtained from the scale varies between 14-70. Getting a high score on the scale is an indication of having a high perceived school life. The internal consistency coefficient Cronbach's Alpha values for the reliability of the scale was in the PSES and its sub-dimensions (SC, AM, AP); It was determined as .83, .69, .67,.67. The scale form was developed for children and adolescents to evaluate themselves. Baytemir et al. (2015) translated the scale into Turkish in the form of perceived school experiences on high school and secondary school students, and the Turkish adaptation was made again. Akin and Sariçam (2014) stated that as a result of the EFA of the scale, the overall scale explained 62.47% of the total variance, the academic pressure dimension 20.06% of the total variance, the academic motivation dimension 21.13% of the total variance, and the school engagement dimension 21.28% of the total variance, they have determined.

2.4.3. The Coach-Athlete Relationship Questionnaire (CART-Q)

The scale is a self-assessment tool developed by Jowett and Ntoumanis (2004) to determine the structure of the coach-athlete relationship and adapted into Turkish by Altıntaş, Kazak-Çetinkalp, and Aşçı (2012). It consists of two forms in the form of athlete and trainer form and 11 items each. In the present study, the athlete form of the scale was used. The scale, which is a 7-point Likert type, can be used in both general dimensions and sub-dimensions. Among its sub-dimensions, closeness consists of 4 items, commitment consists of 3 items, and complementarity consists of 4 items. Its validity and reliability have been tested in many countries. Confirmatory factor analysis was applied to test the construct validity and it was found to be consistent with the original form. While the internal consistency values for the athlete form of the scale vary between 0.82 and 0.90, it varies between 0.69 and 0.78 for the coach form. It has been determined that the inventory is a valid and reliable measurement tool suitable for Turkish culture for coaches and athletes (Altıntaş, Kazak-Çetinkalp & Aşçı, 2012).

2.5. Analysis of Data

The data collected from the research group were interpreted with the statistical package program IBM SPSS 25. Before the analysis -the data was checked with the values of Skewness and Kurtosis (normal distribution of the data) whether the parametric tests met the prerequisites, and it was seen that the data showed a normal distribution. Thus, parametric tests were used in the analysis (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2015). Descriptive statistics (frequency, arithmetic mean, standard deviation) were used as the statistical method, t-test for independent groups, Simple Linear Pearson Correlation analysis and Regression test to determine the relationship between the scales.

3. Results

Table 1: Scores obtained from the of SSWLS, CART-Q, and PSES

Scale	Number of items	n	$\bar{x}$	Sd	Skewness	Kurtosis
SSWLS	5	306	5.63	1.06	-.691	-.163
Closeness	4	306	5.72	1.63	-1.381	1.065
Commitment	3	306	5.35	1.61	-.915	-.090

Complementarity	4	306	5.56	1.53	-1.247	.869
Academic Press	4	306	3.49	0.77	-.532	.376
Academic Motivation	6	306	3.62	0.77	-.441	-.305
School Connectedness	4	306	3.45	0.88	-.567	-.010

In the table below, the descriptive statistical results of the scores obtained from the "The Sport-Specific Satisfaction with Life Scale (SSWLS)", the "The Coach-Athlete Relationship Scale (CART-Q/C-C-C)", and the "The Perceived School Experience Scale (PSES/AP-AM-SC)" are given. Based on the skewness and kurtosis values (Table, 1).

Table 2: T-test Results of SSWLS, CART-Q/C, C, C and PSES/AP/AM/SC by Gender Variables

Scale	Gender	n	$\bar{x}$	Sd	df	t	p	
SSWLS	Famale	189	5.22	1.38	304	4.427	0.00**	
	Male	117	4.96	1.51				
CART-Q	Closeness	Famale	189	5.90	1.53	304	4.154	0.00**
		Male	117	5.64	1.65			
	Commitment	Famale	189	5.48	1.58	304	3.871	0.03*
		Male	117	5.23	1.70			
Complementarity	Famale	189	5.70	1.49	304	4.144	0.00**	
	Male	117	5.45	1.58				
PSES	Academic Press	Famale	189	3.61	0.97	304	1.503	0.13
		Male	117	3.55	1.03			
	Academic Motivation	Famale	189	3.67	0.91	304	.370	0.71
		Male	117	3.66	0.93			
	School Connectedness	Famale	189	3.61	1.00	304	1.213	0.23
		Male	117	3.56	1.01			

*p<0.05, **p<0.01

In Table 2, the t-test results of the students' scores obtained from the Gender-related, "The Sport-Specific Satisfaction with Life Scale (SSWLS)", the "The Coach-Athlete Relationship Scale (CART-Q/C-C-C)", and the "Perceived School Experience Scale (PSES/AP-AM-SC)" are given. While there were significant differences in favor of female participants in the SSWLS and CART-Q (C-C-C) sub-dimensions, no significant difference was found in the PSES/AP-AM-SC dimensions.

Table 3: T-test Results of SSWLS, CART-Q/C, C, C and PSES/AP/AM/SC by the variable of playing in the school team

Scale	School Team	n	$\bar{x}$	Sd	df	t	p	
SSWLS	Yes	192	5.08	1.46	304	2.600	0.00	
	No	114	4.93	1.49				
CART-Q	Closeness	Yes	192	6.16	1.22	304	-2.775	0.00
		No	114	6.47	0.69			
	Commitment	Yes	192	5.65	1.51	304	-2.317	0.02
		No	114	5.99	1.011			
Complementarity	Yes	192	5.96	1.12	304	-2.417	0.01	
	No	114	6.21	0.70				
PSES	Academic Press	Yes	192	3.59	1.01	2948	2.141	0.03
		No	114	3.51	1.01			
	Academic Motivation	Yes	192	3.71	0.91	2948	3.602	0.00
		No	114	3.58	0.93			
	School Connectedness	Yes	192	3.63	1.00	2948	4.257	0.00
		No	114	3.58	1.00			

No	114	3.47	1.00
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*p<0.01

In the table below, the t-test results of the scores obtained from "The Sport-Specific Satisfaction with Life Scale (SSWLS)", the "The Coach-Athlete Relationship Scale (CART-Q/C-C-C)", and the "Perceived School Experience Scale (PSES/AP-AM-SC)" are given according to the variable of "playing in a school team". Significant differences were found in favor of the students in the school team in the SSWLS, sub-dimensions of CART-Q/C-C-C, and PSES/AP-AM-SC (Table 3).

Table 4: Correlation Results between CART-Q and SSWLS

	SSWLS		
	n	r	p
CART-Q	306	0.71	0.00**
Closeness	306	0.69	0.00**
Commitment	306	0.67	0.00**
Complementarity	306	0.70	0.00**

**p<0.01

In Table 4, Pearson Correlation test results are presented in order to test the relationship between "The Sport-Specific Satisfaction with Life" and "The Coach-Athlete Relationship". As can be seen in Table 4, in the correlation analysis between CART-Q and SSWLS, it was observed that there was a high level and significant positive correlation between "SSWLS and sub-dimensions of CART-Q/C-C-C"

Table 5: Correlation Results between PSES and SSWLS

	SSWLS		
	n	r	p
PSES	306	0.56	0.00**
Academic Press	306	0.49	0.00**
Academic Motivation	306	0.50	0.00**
School Connectedness	306	0.45	0.00**

**p<0.01

In Table 5, Pearson Correlation test results are presented in order to test the "Sport-Specific Satisfaction with Life" and "Perceived School Experience". As seen in Table 5, in the correlation analysis performed between perceived school experiences and sportive life satisfaction, it was seen that there was a moderate and significant positive relationship between SSWLS and sub-dimensions of PSES/AP-AM-SC"

Table 6: Regression Results between CART-Q and SSWLS

	B	Standard Error	β	t	P
Constant	1.229	.071		17.218	.000
CART-Q	.687	.012	.714	55.361	.000

R=.714. R²=.510. F_(1,2948) =3064.788

The regression analysis results regarding the prediction of "Sport-Specific Satisfaction with Life" according to the "The Coach-Athlete Relationship" are shown in Table 6. As a result of the regression analysis, it was determined that the coach-athlete relationship was a significant predictor of sport-specific satisfaction with life in athlete students. There is a positive and highly significant relationship (R=0.714) between the coach-athlete relationship of the athlete students and sport-specific satisfaction with life, and the coach-athlete relationship of the students explains 51% of the total variance in their perceptions of their sportive life satisfaction. According to the results of the regression analysis, the equation regarding the prediction of the sport-specific satisfaction with life of the athletes is shown below: Sportive Life Satisfaction= 1.23+0.5* The Coach-Athlete Relationship

Table 7: Regression Results between PSES and SSWLS

	B	Standard Error	β	t	P
Constant	1.612	.095		16.942	.000
PSES	.947	.026	.564	37.040	.000

R=.564. R²=.318. F_(1,2948)=1371.988

The regression analysis results regarding the prediction of “Sport-Specific Satisfaction with Life” according to perceived school experience are shown in Table 7. As can be seen a result of the regression analysis, it was determined that the sport-specific satisfaction with life was a predictor of the school experience perceived in the athlete students. There is a positive and moderately significant relationship (R=0.564) between the athletic students' perceived school experience and their sportive life satisfaction, and students' perceived school experiences explain 32% of the total variance in their perceptions of sportive life satisfaction. According to the results of the regression analysis, the equation regarding the prediction of perceived school experiences is shown below: The Sport-Specific Satisfaction with Life= 1.61+0.5* Perceived School Experiences

4. Discussion

As a result of this research, it was seen that the sports life satisfaction, coach-athlete relationship and perceived school experience of the athlete students were above the average. When the literature is examined, the results of the current research show parallelism. Studies have been found showing that hearing impaired high school athlete students (Somoğlu, 2016) and sports high school students (Somoğlu Yüksek, Kılıçaslan, Sivrikaya & Yazıcı 2017) have high satisfaction with sports life. In addition to studies on people with disabilities such as participation in sports, active sportsmen, participating in physical activities, paralympic olympics athletes and similar studies have shown that doing sports increases the level of life satisfaction. (Yazıcıoğlu, Yavuz, Göktepe, & Tan, 2012; Nemcek, 2016; Tasiemski, Kennedy, Gardner, & Taylor, 2005; Mockevičienė & Savenkoviene, 2012; Ziolkowski, Zubrzycki, Blachnio, Drobnik, Zaranska, & Moska, 2016).

For many athletes, the quality of the coach-athlete relationship characterizes the athletes' entire sporting experience (Poczwadowski, Barott, & Henschen, 2002). When the literature is examined, studies show that the coach-athlete relationship is high in a positive sense (Avcı, Çepikkurt & Kale, 2018; Bülbül, 2019; Güllü, 2018; Özşaker, Sarı & Omrak, 2016; Selağzı & Çepikkurt, 2015). It has been concluded that football players (Tolukan & Akyel, 2019) and students in high school sports teams (Keskin et al., 2018) have positive coach-athlete relations. This finding can be interpreted as the high level of relationship between athlete students and their coaches. In other words, if it is high, the athlete focuses on the task, makes more effort and enjoys training; when it is low, they conclude that reluctance in training, less struggle, and a sense of superiority.

When the arithmetic means and standard deviation of the scores obtained from the PSES and its sub-dimensions of the athlete students are evaluated, it is seen that the scores obtained from the total and sub-dimensions of PSES are above the average. This finding can be interpreted as the students' perceptions about school, their commitment to school, their academic motivation and academic pressure levels are high. In the study conducted by Güler (2019), it is seen that the data are above the average. Whitley (1999), in his longitudinal study among high schools between 1993 and 1996, found that their course achievement was high and they had a high graduation rate, and that their absenteeism rates, disciplinary problems, and dropout rates were low. Therefore, it can be said that participation in sports activities increases school experience perceptions.

Athlete students' sportive life satisfaction and coach-athlete relations and all sub-dimensions differed in favor of female participants, but there was no significant difference between men and women in school experiences. The reason why there is a significant relationship between sportive life satisfaction in favor of female students is that female students in Turkish societies generally have a structure that does not welcome female students to spend time at home and do sports. It can be said that these students who have the opportunity to do sports show higher life satisfaction than their other peers. When the results of the sportive life satisfaction literature were examined, it was found that the studies supporting the research findings (Dikmen, 1995; Duman, Baştuğ, Taşgın, & Akandere, 2011; Danielsen, Samdal, Hetland & World, 2009) had higher life satisfaction in favor of women.

Again, significant results were found in favor of undergraduate students (Yıldırım, 2017) and women participating in physical activity (Baştuğ & Duman, 2010).

The coach-athlete relationship is largely characterized as "emotional tone". (Jowett & Cockerill, 2003; Salminen & Liukkonen, 1996). Some studies with male and female athletes show that men focus on winning and performance; showed that women value relationships and communication (Gill, 2004; Holmes, McNeil, Adorna, & Procaccino, 2008). The reason why female students have higher coach-athlete relationships in the CART-Q sub-factors may be due to the fact that female students are more emotional, prone to attachment and attach more importance to relationships than boys.

Different research findings stand out in the literature on perceived school experiences. In the study conducted by Güler (2019), it was stated that female students had a higher perceived school life. Özkara and Kalkavan (2018) found a significant difference in favor of female students in the dimension of academic pressure in their study called perceived school experiences of sports high school students. Considering the literature review results, it is in favor of female participants in America and Europe (Butcher, Iachini & Amorese, 2007; Misra, McKean, West & Russo, 2000; Snyder & Dillow, 2010) and in eastern societies (Chen, 2008; Hong-Fincher, 2014; Ramaprabou & Dash, 2018; Tian & Lu, 2017) we see in studies that they see higher academic pressure in favor of male students. The reason why there was no significant difference in perceived school experiences in the current study may be that the school experiences did not differ according to gender, since both genders had their own preferences in choosing to study at high schools.

When the research findings were evaluated according to the status of playing in the school team, there was a significant difference in the sportive life satisfaction of the athlete students and their perceived school experiences in favor of those playing in the school team, while a significant difference was found in favor of the students who did not play in the school team in the coach-athlete relationship and all sub-dimensions. In other words, the student's sportive life satisfaction and perceived school experience are high, and the coach-athlete relationship is low. Somoğlu (2021) found significant differences in the dimension of commitment to coach-athlete relationship, perceived school experience total and sub-dimensions, and sportive life satisfaction according to being in the school team. Being a part of the school teams of the athletic students can be interpreted as they increase their school experience, they are more attached to the school, they have more academic motivation and they experience less academic pressure. Extracurricular sports activities, including school sports, have a motivating feature for students to lead an active life. The reason for the low trainer-athlete relations of the students in the school team may be that they do not equate the sports trainer or physical education and sports teacher at the school with the trainers in sports clubs.

It was determined that there was a high level and significant positive relationship between the coach-athlete relationship/sub-dimensions (CART-Q/C-C-C) and sportive life satisfaction. It can be interpreted that the positive relationship established between these two increases the sports life satisfaction of the athletes, in other words, it improves the well-being and psychological state of the athletes. The subjective well-being scores of the athletes and their coach-athlete relationship scores were evaluated, and the subjective well-being scores of the athletes in both branches (taekwondo, protected football) and the three sub-dimensions of the coach-athlete relationship inventory (closeness, loyalty, Complementarity) was found to have a moderately significant positive correlation between the scores obtained (Gönen, 2019). In his study, in which Mangan (2018) adapted the life satisfaction scale to sports, he found that there was a high level of positive correlation between the coach-athlete relationship and life satisfaction. To sum up, it can be explained that as the level of coach-athlete relationship increases, the sports life satisfaction levels of the athletes also increase. In this research, it was determined that there was a positive, moderate and significant relationship between perceived school experiences and sportive life satisfaction. It can be said that the school experiences of the athletic students are moderately related to their sportive life satisfaction and it affects their sportive life satisfaction. The concepts of happiness and subjective well-being are used as synonyms in the literature (Diener, Scollon & Lucas, 2009). It has been determined that the level of happiness of adolescent students increases as their interest in school increases, and the level of happiness decreases as the level of interest towards school decreases (Aypay & Eryılmaz, 2011; Baytemir, 2019; Doğan & Çelik, 2014; Elmore & Huebner, 2010). Furlong, You, Renshaw, O'Malley, & Rebelez, (2013) and

Pennell, Boman, and Mergler (2015) stated that there was a significant relationship between the positive environment created by positive experiences at school and students' well-being. In another study conducted with sports high school students, it was determined that there were positive and high-level relationships between the attitudes towards sports and its sub-dimensions (interest in sports, living with sports and active sports) and school climate perception (Göktaş & Şentürk, 2019).

It has been determined that the coach-athlete relationship and perceived school experiences are significant predictors of sportive life satisfaction. It has been revealed that the coach-athlete relationship of the athlete students explains 51% of the sportive life satisfaction, and the perceived school experience explains 36% of the sportive life satisfaction. The result shows that the relationship between the coach-athlete and the perceived school experiences of the athlete students have an important role on their sportive life satisfaction. School satisfaction is one of the important areas of satisfaction that makes students happy in their lives (Casas, Bello, González, & Aligué, 2013; Telef, Arslan, Mert, & Kalafat, 2015). School satisfaction is a subjective and cognitive evaluation of how school life is perceived (Baker, Dilly, Aupperlee, & Patil, 2003). School satisfaction, gratitude, enthusiasm for life, optimism and perseverance explain 24% of middle school students' happiness (Telef, 2020). Göktaş and Şentürk (2019) reported that the attitude towards sports explains approximately 98% of the total variance in the perception of school climate.

5. Conclusion

High school students' coach-athlete relationships, school experiences and sportive life satisfaction are above the medium level. Sportive life satisfaction is explained by 51% coach-athlete relationship and 36% by perceived school experiences. It is seen that students' coach-athlete relationships and perceived school experiences positively affect their sportive life satisfaction. For this reason, students are required to take part in sports activities and sports competitions and sports events need to be organized. Families, teachers and administrators should support students in directing them to sports and they should be encouraged by the people in charge to act consciously in this regard. In this context, students' coaches, school administrators, teachers and families can be encouraged to carry out the school and sports together by adopting those sports are an important tool in increasing the psychological well-being of the students, the development of relationships, their commitment to the school and developing positive emotions. In addition, suitable course hours and training programs can be arranged for dual-career students (athlete-student). Considering the positive effect of sports participation on the coach-athlete relationship and sports-specific life satisfaction of students, it may be beneficial for families and competent people to follow a guiding role in ensuring that students participate in sports activities. Coaches and physical education teachers can increase school sports activities and diversify sports branches, and enable students to participate in school sports activities. By increasing the types of sports activities that students participate in, studies can be carried out for the types of sports activities that will appeal to wider audiences.

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